

THE FEATURES OF TRANSLATING OF ONOMASTIC COMPONENTS
USING THE MAIN CONTENT OF LANGUAGE STRUCTURE

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Annotation: *The article analyzes the features of translation of onomastic components using the main content of language structure.. The main focus is given on some methods of translation of antroponyms and toponyms from the English into Uzbek languages.*

Key words: *antroponyms, toponyms, transcription, transliteration, , national, identity.*

It is an undeniable fact that onomastic components serve as lexical units which can't be freely made up in speech but they are reproduced as ready-made units. There existed several types of lexical units comprising personal names, flora and fauna, geographical proper names and etc. All onomastic components are permeated with cultural and historical content, since its subject matter is language, which is a condition, basis and product of culture”, and through delivering adequate translation linguists contribute to a higher level of cross-cultural awareness. It should be noted that the set of rules for transcription from English into Russian has been developed quite fully, and the rules for transcription of English-language names are reflected in many publications, including dictionaries [Dudareva N.A., 2003; 148], however, the rules for transcription from English into Uzbek or from Uzbek into English are not fully developed, and, basically, translators rely on the rules for translating transcription from English into Russian and use similar techniques. For example, anthroponyms are usually rendered through transcription or transliteration: *Thomas Heywood – Томас Хейвуд, George Gordon Byron – Жорж Гордон Байрон*. These days preference is given to

transcription. The names of kings are of special interest, as they are traditional in form: *King Charles* – *Қирол Карл*, *King James* – *Қирол Яков*, *King George* – *Қирол Георг*), *King William* – *Қирол Вилгелм*, *King Louis* – *Қирол Людвик*, *King Henrie/Henry* – *Қирол Генрих*. [Proshina Z.G., 2008; 118-119]. Toponyms are normally transcribed or transliterated: *Oxford* – *Оксфорд*. Also, there can be two versions of translation which are both of acceptable like rendering in Russian *Stratford-on-Avon* - *Статфорд-на-Авоне* or *Стратфорд-он-Эйвон*.

Some geographical names can be translated by calques: *Rocky Mountains* – *Қояли тепаликлар*, *Saint Helena Island* – *Муқаддас Елена ороли*, *Golden Horn Bay*–*Олтин Шох қўлтиғи*. Half-calques can be used to translate toponyms with classifiers, such as *river*, *lake*, *bridge*: *Waterloo Bridge* – *Ватерлоо кўприғи*, *Salt Lake City* – *Солт-Лэйк-Сити шаҳари*.

Sometimes proper names are literally translated using calques. Here are examples of the translation of proper names into English of the work of Yusuf Khass Hajib "Kutadgubilig" ("Wisdom of Royal Glory"), translated by Robert Dankoff. *Одгурмыш* – *Wide Awake* (букв.: *Осмотрительный*) *Айтолды* – *Full Moon* (букв.: *Полная луна*) *Кюнтоғды* – *King Rising Sun* (букв.: *Король поднимающегося солнца*) *Огдюльмиш* – *Highly Praised* (букв.: *Высоко восхваленный*). Proper names of persons, geographic names are used without special interpretation, since they are not difficult to determine by context. Let us illustrate what has been mentioned above with examples:

<p><i>Аввали, ҳаммасидан олдингиси</i> Отиқ эди, <i>Худога тўла содиқ, кўнгли ва кўзи тўғри эди. Моли, тани-жонини қурбон қилди, Фақат расулнинг севинчини(гина)тилади. Сўнг, киши(лар)нинг сараси Форуқ эди, Тили ва кўнгли бирдек, халқнинг асили эди. Бу маслахатчи, ҳидоят</i></p>	<p><i>First of all was Atik (Abu Bakr): he believed in God and straightened his heart and tongue; he ransomed all – wealth, body, soul – seeking only the Prophet’s pleasure. Then there was Faruq (Umar), best of men: his tongue and heart were one; he was the foundation and the pillar of the true</i></p>
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<p>қилувчи, дин учун кўрк эди, У шариат юзидан парда кўтарди, яъни шариатни халққа тушунтирди. Кейингиси Усмон эди, андишали, мулойим эди, Кишилар орасида сараси, сахий, очиқ кўл эди. Борини, нарсаларини ва ўзини фидо қилди, Паёмбар унга икки қизини берди. Бундан бошқа сараси Али эди, Кўрқмас, ботир, юракли, ақли тўла эди [Yusuf Khass Hajib, K.Karimov, 1971].</p>	<p><i>Religion; he raised the veil from the face of the holy Law. After him came Uthman: modest and pure, choice among men and most generous: he ransomed wealth and self; and the Prophet gave him his two daughters. Finally, there was Ali, brave and manly and clever: his hand was liberal and his heart was alert; wise and pious was he; he achieved a great name [Yusuf Khass Hajib, Robert Dankoff, 1983].</i></p>
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The study of onomastic components as lexical units in languages of different structures in order to identify common human and national characteristics is acquiring more and more theoretical and practical significance. The onomastic units along with other linguistic units convey national identity, the paradigm of national knowledge where the study of translation techniques of proper and geographical names is of great importance. In this regard, within the framework of the modern scientific paradigm, there is a need to study lexical units, both from the standpoint of their translation and from the standpoint of their conceptualization of the world, since they reflect the national characteristics of people.

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